

disappearance of the broad band at ~ 2620 and $\sim 1140\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, indicates the deprotonation of carboxylic hydrogen and sulphonic acid hydrogen and its participation in coordination¹⁴. The presence of water of crystallisation is indicated in the spectra of Ni^{II} complexes of 2-FMCKA, 2-FGED and 2-FGSAA because there is a peak at $3190\text{--}3290\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The new bands observed in the complexes at ~ 470 and $\sim 410\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, respectively¹⁵. The ir spectra of Ni^{II} complex of 2-FGED show the presence of bidentate chelating nitrate group¹⁶.

Screening of fungicidal activity: The antifungal activity of the compounds was checked by food-poison technique. Seven days old culture of *Helminthosporium gramineum* (causing stripe disease in barley), *Syncephalostrum racemosus* (causing fruit rot of tomato) and *Colleotrichium capsici* (causing die back disease in chillies) were used as test organism which were grown on potato dextrose-agar medium. The fungi were grown at $28 \pm 2^\circ$ and the average of three replications was recorded. The percentage inhibition¹⁷ was calculated as $100 \times (C - T)/C$ where, C = diameter of fungus colony in control plate and T = diameter of fungus colony in test plate. All the complexes and ligands were found to be highly active against all the fungi tested (Table 1). The metal complexes were more active in all the cases than their ligands, which is in accordance with the previous established fact that chelation of metal to ligand increases the fungitoxicity of the molecule¹⁸.

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X-Ray Diffraction Studies on Tris(1,2-diaminopropane)nickel(II) Tungstate

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IN continuation to our investigation¹ on Ni^{II} complexes with unsaturated amines as ligands we here-in report the powder X-ray diffraction data for the complex tris(1,2-diaminopropane)nickel(II) tungstate.

Experimental

The experimental details, elemental analyses, magnetic, visible and ir spectral data have already been reported in earlier communication¹. The X-ray data were recorded at the University of Aberdeen, Scotland, U.K. on a Phillips X-ray machine attached with a diffractogram. The diffraction pattern was recorded at a chart speed $2^\circ (2\theta)/\text{min}$ at $5\text{--}60^\circ (2\theta)$ using the scale, $1^\circ = 1\text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of the title compound suggest the molecular formula as $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2)_3\text{WO}_4$.

The diffractogram has been shown in Fig. 1 which records in all 18 reflections between 5 and $60^\circ (2\theta)$ with maxima at $2\theta = 10.1^\circ$ which corresponds to $d = 8.7576\text{ \AA}$. The 2θ values for prominent peaks have been listed in Table 1. All main peaks have been indexed and their $\sin^2\theta$ values compared with the calculated ones. Comparison of the values reveal that there is a good agreement between calculated and observed values of $\sin^2\theta$. The unit cell has been calculated by the trial and error method²⁻⁴. The observed values fit well in the tetragonal system to give a unit cell with lattice constants, $a = 12.3853\text{ \AA}$, $C = 12.9269\text{ \AA}$ and cell volume $1982.930\text{ \AA}^3$. Substitution of this cell volume primitive lattice ($n=4$) gives the theoretical value of density equal to 1.7711 g cm^{-3} . The experimental

Fig. 1. Diffractogram.

TABLE 1—X-RAY DATA OF THE COMPLEX

Peak no.	d Spacing Å	Relative intensity $\times 100 I/I_0$	Observed $\sin^2 \theta$	Calcd. $\sin^2 \theta$	(hkl)
1	8.757 7	100 0	0.007 7	0.007 7	(110)
2	6.468 4	22.5	0.014 2	0.014 2	(002)
3	5.089 0	95.6	0.023 4	0.022 9	(211)
4	4.358 5	89.5	0.031 96	0.030 99	(220)
				0.032 0	(008)
5	3.951 5	48.3	0.038 06	0.038 4	(301)
				0.038 7	(310)
6	3.547 7	60.9	0.047 2	0.047 5	(203)
7	3.266 6	18.6	0.055 7	0.056 9	(004)
8	3.099 8	17.6	0.061 8	0.061 9	(400)
9	2.857 7	7.5	0.072 8	0.073 8	(331)
10	2.722 3	11.9	0.080 2	0.081 0	(421)
11	2.629 2	3.4	0.085 9	0.083 9	(332)
				0.087 8	(224)
12	2.488 0	20.0	0.096 0	0.096 8	(500)
13	2.404 4	4.5	0.102 7	0.104 3	(205)
				0.107 4	(833)
14	2.320 8	6.7	0.110 3	0.109 5	(423)
				0.111 1	(502)
15	2.237 8	14.7	0.118 6	0.119 8	(225)
				0.118 8	(404)
16	1.972 9	5.5	0.152 7	0.153 7	(504)
				0.150 9	(405)
17	1.884 2	8.8	0.167 4	0.169 2	(524)
				0.166 7	(316)
18	1.752 3	8.2	0.193 5	0.193 7	(710)
				0.193 4	(701)

$A=0.0038742$, $a=12.3^{\circ}53 \text{ \AA}$, $C=0.0035563$, $c=12.9269 \text{ \AA}$, cell volume = $1982.980 \text{ \AA}^3$, mol. wt. = 522.55, density (calcd) = 1.7711 g cm^{-3} ($n=4$), density (obs) = 1.8232 g cm^{-3} .

value of density of the complex has been found to be 1.8232 g cm^{-3} which is fairly in good agreement within the limits of the experimental error.

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Copper(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes of Schiff Bases derived from Amino-thiazole

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In this paper we report the isolation and characterisation of four new terdentate Schiff base ligands derived from 4-*p*-ethoxyphenyl-2-aminothiazole and substituted-salicylaldehyde (5-methyl (A), 5-chloro (B), 5-bromo (C)) or β -hydroxynaphthaldehyde (D) and their complexes with Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} .

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